

EFFECT OF BASALT FIBRE HYBRIDIZATION ON THE LOW VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

In recent years, fibres in textile forms have been introduced for use in composites to exploit the advantages of textile structures, such as better dimensional stability and deep-draw shapability [1]. During their service life, composites are subjected to various loading conditions and low velocity impact is one of the most critical because it induces widespread damage, which reduces the strength of composite materials. Due to their high specific stiffness and strength, carbon reinforced polymer composites are widely used in aerospace industry. However, the toughness of carbon fibre is quite low and the resulting damage resistance is poor. In this regard, several researchers have successfully adopted hybridization approach with high strain to failure fibres to improve the damage resistance of composites. In particular, glass fibres are the best option from the viewpoint of cost, availability, and ease of processing, and hybrid carbon/glass fibre composites have consistently demonstrated better damage tolerance under impact than their carbon fibre counterparts [2-4]. In recent years basalt fibres have gained an increasing attention as possible replacement of conventional glass fibres [5] due to their advantages in terms of environmental cost and chemical-physical properties. Mineral fibres obtained from basalt rocks are not new, but their suitability as reinforcement in polymer composites is a relatively new issue [6]. Despite this growing interest, only scarce attention has been devoted to the low-velocity impact behaviour of these classes of composites. Residual structural properties are

another important consequence of impacts on a laminate because they directly influence the way in which the structure can bear service loads.

In this study woven basalt-carbon/epoxy hybrid composites were fabricated in interply hybrid structures and subjected to low-velocity impact using a drop weight apparatus. Specimens were impacted and the influence of impact energy on their flexural residual strength was assessed by quasi-static four point bending tests.

Post impact effects were evaluated using non-destructive tests such as ultrasonic phased array and acoustic emission (AE). Ultrasonic testing was carried out after impact to evaluate the role played by basalt fibre hybridization on the extent of damaged area. Instead the acoustic emission (AE) was carried out to understand the role played by basalt fibre hybridization on the mechanical behaviour after impact of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. Furthermore, interlaminar shear strength for all the hybrids was investigated.

2. Materials and methods

Plain weave basalt (BAS 220.1270.P supplied by Basaltex-Flocart NV, Belgium) and carbon (CC160 supplied by Saati Composites, Italy) fabrics were used to reinforce a bi-component epoxy resin (EC157+W152 MR, supplied by Elantas Camattini, Italy). The areal densities were 220 g/m² for basalt fabrics and 160 g/m² for carbon ones. All laminates were manufactured by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) and cured for 12h at room temperature and 4h at 70 °C. All configurations were produced using

thirteen fabric layers keeping constant the volume fraction (0.32 ± 0.01), so that the thickness of all the produced configurations was almost constant (3.40 ± 0.15 mm). Two hybrid configurations were manufactured: in the first one (BC-HS) fabrics were stacked as a sandwich-like sequence with seven carbon fibre layers (core) and three basalt fibre layers (skins) for each side of the laminate, while in the second configuration (BC-HI) seven layers of basalt fabrics and six of carbon fabrics were alternatively stacked, keeping basalt fabrics as outer layers. Not hybridized basalt (B) and carbon (C) reinforced epoxy composites were also manufactured as reference configurations. Specimens ($180 \text{ mm} \times 60 \text{ mm} \times 3.4 \text{ mm}$) were cut from 300 mm-wide square laminates and then used for the mechanical characterisation. Four-point bending tests were carried out on five specimens for each configuration according to ASTM D 6272. A span-to-depth ratio of 23:1 and a cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/min were used. Flexural modulus was calculated through the measurement of strain by strain gauges. Specimens were tested in bending both as they were produced (non impacted samples) and after they were impacted at low-velocity, in order to measure their residual flexural strength. Impact tests were performed by using a falling dart impact testing machine, model Fractovis Plus from CEAST (Pianezza - TO, Italy), equipped with a circular sample holder (external and internal diameters equal to 60 mm and 40 mm, respectively). Specimens were tested at three impact energies (5 J, 12.5 J and 25 J) by keeping constant the indenter mass (6.929 kg) with an hemispherical impact head (diameter equal to 12.7 mm). The impact energies were selected in order to avoid that damage exceeded samples width. The extent of damaged area after the impact was determined using non-destructive ultrasonic inspection equipment OmniScan MX with standard phased array probe 3.5 MHz, linear array, 64 elements. The interlaminar shear strength was evaluated according to ASTM D 2344. Ten specimens having dimensions equal to $20 \text{ mm} \times 6.8 \text{ mm} \times 3.4 \text{ mm}$ ($L \times W \times t$) were tested for each laminate. The span-to-depth ratio and the cross-head speed were set to 4:1 and 1 mm/min, respectively. All the mechanical tests (both flexural and interlaminar ones) were performed on a Z010 from Zwick/Roell (Ulm, Germany) universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell. Flexural

tests were monitored by acoustic emission until final fracture occurred using an AMSY-5 AE system by Vallen Systeme GmbH (Icking, Germany). The AE acquisition settings used throughout this experimental work were as follows: threshold = 35 dB, rearm Time (RT) = 0.4 ms, Duration Discrimination Time (DDT) = 0.2 ms and total gain = 34 dB. The acquisition threshold was selected after 30 minutes recording of background noise with the AE setup configuration actually used, and was set 6 dB above the maximum level of recorded spurious signal from the electronic system. To allow linear localization of signals, two broad-band PZT AE sensors (100-1500 kHz, model 1045S, from Fujicera, Japan) were placed at both ends of specimens using silicon grease for coupling.

3. Results and discussion

The mechanical behaviour of composites depends on several factors that can be related to both materials used for the matrix and the reinforcement and geometrical parameters such as lay-up configuration and laminate thickness. Obviously the process of damage also depends on the kind of system used for testing, namely the loading geometry and the impact velocity. All these issues make the damage process a complex combination of energy absorption mechanisms such as matrix cracking, transverse fibre fracture and delamination. As shown in Fig. 1, it is possible to perceive the different response of the tested laminates by inspecting the morphology of impacted surfaces.

Fig. 1. Front/back images of different laminates impacted at 25J.

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Drop-weight impact test at 25J on C composite showed penetration of the dart through its thickness with splitting on the back face, highlighting the brittle fracture of carbon laminate. In the same impact condition, B composite exhibited cross-shaped cracks and debonding on the front face with associated matrix cracking and back surface splitting but without evidence of penetration. BC-HI and BC-HS laminates exhibited an intermediate behaviour between not-hybrid composites, although different patterns were detected as a consequence of the different lay-ups. The damaged area for BC-HI laminate was larger than that of BC-HS one, suggesting that the former can absorb more energy. Both hybrid laminates showed bulge on the back surface as a consequence of matrix cracking and pull-out of outer fibre layers but the damage pattern was quite different. The BC-HS laminates exhibited an impact behaviour more similar to B ones because the three outer layers, being made of basalt, prevented extensive fibre breakage unlike the C composites. Conversely, the impacted BC-HI exhibited back surface damages approaching the pattern of C laminate but without penetration. This was related to the presence of alternating basalt layers which provided enhanced compliance. To assess composite impact damage it is common to refer to two key parameters, namely the impact energy (E_i) and absorbed energy (E_a). Impact energy is the kinetic energy of the impactor right before contact between samples and impactor takes place, whereas absorbed energy is the energy dissipated by the system through several mechanisms like elastic deformation, friction, plastic deformation and, most importantly, by mechanisms which are peculiar to the material (matrix cracking, debonding, pull-out, fibre breakage). In most of tested samples, penetration did not occur and the impactor rebounded with an energy that is the difference between E_i and E_a .

The absorbed energy can be calculated from force-displacement curves (Fig. 2). When force-displacement curves show a closed pattern (meaning that the impactor was rebounded) the area enclosed within the ascending and descending branches of the curve represents the absorbed energy. Indeed if the displacement returns toward the axis origin during unloading, it means that some elastic energy is recovered by the laminate. Carbon laminates have been the only laminates to be perforated at 25J not

showing any energy recovery (Fig. 2c: displacement increases while force decreases), while basalt containing composites have shown a residual elastic response.

Basalt and hybrid laminates absorbed more energy through higher overall deformation, being more compliant, and through delaminations.

Fig. 2. Force–displacement response for impacted laminates at 5J (a); 12.5J (b); 25J (c).

In order to assess the damage accumulated by the materials it is necessary to introduce a parameter called damage degree defined as the ratio E_a/E_i ,

which has a value lower than unity until penetration is reached. Fig. 3 shows the damage degree as a function of impact energy for the different laminate configurations. It is evident that damage degree of carbon-epoxy laminate increased dramatically moving from 5J to 12.5J, and reached unity at 25J. This is a further confirmation of the inherent brittleness of C laminate, which cannot absorb high impact energy because of its abrupt and catastrophic damage mechanism. Damage degree of basalt containing laminates increased with the impact energy, reaching a maximum value of ~ 0.86 for the BC-HI composite. This suggests a positive role played by basalt fibre hybridization, which improved the impact energy absorption.

Fig. 3. Damage degree progression of tested composite laminates.

The ultrasonic C-scan testing method was carried out to evaluate damaged area that is supposed to be connected with the energy absorbed by the samples. Figure 4 shows C scan images of different samples impacted at 12.5J from which it was possible to estimate the extent of damage. The results are summarized in table 1. It has been difficult to assess the damage caused by the impactor because of the additional damage introduced by the circular holder beneath the samples during impact tests. This was particularly true for the basalt laminates. This can explain why the data for basalt laminates in table 1 do not exhibit a clear trend with increasing impact energy.

On the whole, all the examined samples showed a progression in damaged area with increasing impact energy, though the behaviour of the various laminates was quite different.

Fig. 4. Typical ultrasonic C-scan images of 12.5J impacted C samples (a); BC-HI samples (b); BC-HS samples (c); B samples (d).

The carbon fibre reinforced laminate exhibited a small damaged area, confirming that C composite absorbs impact load in a brittle way. Among the

basalt fabric reinforced composites (hybridized or not) the BC-HI and BC-HS showed a wider damaged area suggesting that delamination between different kinds of layers can improve impact energy absorption behaviour. It is clear that BC-HI composite, owing to the higher number of basalt/carbon interfaces, seemed to dissipate impact energy in a wider area through multiple damage events.

		Impact Energy (J)		
		5	12.5	25
Specimen type	C	298	736	-
	BC-HI	690	966	1027
	BC-HS	594	603	999
	B	310	1048	889

Tab. 1. Averaged damaged area in mm² for each type of specimen and different impact energies.

With regard to interlaminar shear strength, it is worth remembering that this characteristic depends on many parameters such as a) adhesion between matrix and fibre, b) constitutive materials, c) fibre volume fraction and d) stacking sequence. Fig. 5 shows that B laminate exhibited the worst interlaminar shear strength whereas C laminate exhibited the best one. This result might be view as a consequence of a better interfacial bonding between carbon and epoxy matrix than the one between basalt and epoxy. Hybridization led to a better interlaminar shear strength only in the BC-HS case. The basalt fibre hybridization affected also the flexural strength and flexural modulus of laminates, both before and after impact. Carbon/epoxy composites were stiffer than basalt/epoxy ones as the carbon fibres had higher elastic modulus than basalt ones (Tab. 2). Flexural tests on specimens impacted at 12.5J (Fig. 6) highlighted that hybrid composites had flexural stiffness intermediate between carbon/epoxy and basalt/epoxy ones.

The different lay-up of the hybrid composites played an important role on the laminate stiffness. Although carbon layers are stiffer than basalt ones and although BC-HI has less carbon layers than BC-HS, the former possessed higher flexural modulus among basalt containing composites. This is due to the fact that in the sandwich structure the layers bearing the bending load are mainly the outer ones, which in

BC-HS samples are made of basalt (less stiff than carbon).

Fig. 5. Interlaminar shear strength of composite laminates

Hybridization also induced improved toughness and flexural strength. C composites showed a higher flexural strength than B ones after 12.5J impact (Fig. 6), but hybridized configurations allowed to strongly improve both flexural strength and toughness with respect to carbon laminates, and the sandwich configuration seemed to represent the best compromise between these two competing requirements.

Fig. 6. Typical stress vs. strain curves for flexural tests on composites previously impacted at 12.5J

This happens because sandwich structure has a higher number of carbon layers which possess higher ultimate strength than basalt ones. Thus the flexural strength is more influenced by the fibre mechanical properties rather than by composite stacking sequence. Although the non-impacted laminates can be ranked from the higher to the lower

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flexural strength in the following order: C>BC-HS>BC-HI>B (Tab. 2), the trend was quite different for impacted samples, in particular as the impact energy increased.

Specimen	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)
Non-impacted		
B	229.34±3.24	14.35±0.75
C	593.48±9.57	38.70±0.10
BC-HI	350.84±0.30	25.84±2.78
BC-HS	418.68±8.10	24.20±1.42
Impact Energy: 5 J		
B	218.64±3.76	14.16±0.34
C	349.01±35.80	33.12±0.94
BC-HI	345.21±22.14	25.23±0.07
BC-HS	369.58±5.55	21.99±1.37
Impact Energy: 12.5 J		
B	207.30±3.09	13.55±0.49
C	238.59±0.50	27.29±0.27
BC-HI	304.45±8.07	23.64±0.10
BC-HS	316.77±0.79	20.59±0.06
Impact Energy: 25 J		
B	142.55±3.92	11.48±0.64
C	-	-
BC-HI	259.72±2.80	20.90±0.22
BC-HS	250.79±13.45	18.58±0.03

Tab. 2. Summary of flexural properties for basalt, carbon and hybrid composites

It should be noted that the increase of impact energy led to an increase of the damaged area, which in turn reduced both flexural strength and flexural stiffness. In order to obtain a better indication of the damage tolerance (residual properties after impact) the normalized flexural strength (or stiffness) of each specimen was calculated as the ratio of the mean strength (or stiffness) of the impacted specimen to the mean value of the flexural strength (or stiffness) of the undamaged specimen. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the normalized flexural strength and flexural stiffness with respect to the increasing impact energy, respectively.

After being impacted at 12.5J, the C laminate lost almost 60% of its early flexural strength and almost 30% of its early flexural stiffness whereas the impact at 25J led to penetration with catastrophic

failure, confirming the worst damage resistance and tolerance capabilities among all considered laminate configurations.

Fig. 7. Normalized residual flexural strength as a function of increasing impact energy

Fig. 8. Normalized residual flexural stiffness as a function of increasing impact energy

This behaviour was due to the characteristic energy absorption mechanism of C composites, which dissipated energy mainly by fast transverse crack propagation and fibre fracture. B composite showed a better behaviour with a more gradual degradation pattern because the impact energy was mostly absorbed by the interface failures occurring among laminate layers and at the fibre/matrix interface. It is evident the positive role played by basalt fabric on the post-impact characteristics of hybrid laminates. More specifically, BC-HI presented the most favourable degradation pattern as it showed the best damage tolerance (Fig. 7 and 8). The BC-HS laminate, although presenting higher quasi-static

flexural properties when compared to BC-HI (Tab. 2), exhibited a steeper damage resistance drop (Fig. 7). This has been related to the energy dissipation mechanism of BC-HI through multiple small delaminations between dissimilar layers (Fig. 9a) whereas the BC-HS dissipated the energy mainly through transverse crack propagation in carbon “core” of sandwich laminate and secondly through main delaminations at the basalt-skin/carbon-core interface (Fig. 9b), as confirmed by AE monitoring.

Fig. 9. Close-up view of (a) BC-HI and (b) BC-HS specimens impacted at 12.5J after flexural test

The time evolution and nature of different failure modes of composites have been studied through the analysis of acoustic emission signals recorded in real time during flexural tests on non-impacted and impacted composite laminates. Basalt (B) and carbon (C) laminates exhibited a different response to impact loading in terms of damage degree and damage tolerance. This behaviour suggested that the mechanisms responsible for the energy absorption were dissimilar. For non-impacted C laminates, very few AE signals were recorded until final fracture occurred, thus confirming the catastrophic and localized failure (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Typical AE amplitude vs. time response during flexural test on undamaged carbon laminates

Most of AE signals had amplitudes in the range 35–50 dB, which are usually ascribed to matrix cracking, while few signals could be ascribed to fibre breakages (80-100 dB) and interfacial failures (55-65 dB) (Fig. 11) [7-9]. This behaviour is consistent with the dominant failure mode of these composites mainly due to multiple matrix cracks localized in the tensile side. The failure of carbon composites resulted to be therefore characterized by the nucleation of matrix cracks, which then triggered debonding phenomena and further transverse cracks leading to fibre failures. From the localization plots of AE signals (Fig. 12) it can be inferred that the extent of the damaged zone responsible for the intense acoustic emission activity was wide, as confirmed by the micrograph in the inset of Fig. 12. The impact damage caused an early onset of acoustic emission activity (signals of low amplitude and short duration) and a higher number of signals. This trend increased with increasing impact energy (Fig. 13). Impact loading caused, in brittle carbon laminates, an unstable damage in terms of matrix cracks and small debonding phenomena, which became active at lower stresses during the subsequent flexural loading. Most AE signals were still localized in the lower amplitude range (< 55 dB) thus confirming the same failure modes observed in non-impacted laminates even though the presence of impact damage seemed to quicken the process thanks to the splitting in the rear face. This thesis is supported by the localization of AE signals (Fig. 14), which appeared to be similar to the one observed for non-impacted laminates (Fig. 12).

Fig. 11. Typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on undamaged carbon laminates

Fig. 12. Acoustic emission localization plot for undamaged carbon laminates. The inset represents a close-up view of typical failure modes for undamaged carbon laminates

Basalt laminates showed a different behaviour, which was characterized by significant AE signals since the beginning of loading also for the undamaged material (Fig. 15). These signals can be attributed to matrix cracks and interface failures. Compared with carbon laminates, an increase in the number of signals in the range 65-75 dB (pull-out) was observed (Fig. 16). This suggests that interface failures seem to be the dominant failure mechanism, which was mainly localized in the compression side. This can explain the lower strength of basalt/epoxy laminates compared to carbon ones.

Failure in basalt laminates took place in compressed half section, whilst in carbon laminates the whole section was involved in the fracture process up to the tensile face. The fracture surface in basalt laminates exhibited the presence of a typical fracture pattern due to compression failure, consisting of fibre microbuckling and kink bands (inset in Fig. 16).

Fig. 13. Typical AE amplitude vs. time response during flexural test on carbon laminates impacted at 12.5J

Fig. 14. Acoustic emission localization plot for carbon laminates impacted at 12.5J

Fig. 15. Typical AE amplitude vs. time response during flexural test on undamaged basalt laminates

The damaged zone so nucleated can cause longitudinal splitting leading to premature failure of the composite laminates thus preventing higher stresses in the outermost tensile fibres to be reached. Fibre microbuckling is known to occur preferentially in systems characterized by medium interface strength [10].

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Fig. 16. Typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on undamaged basalt laminates. The inset represents a close-up view of typical failure modes for undamaged basalt laminates

As for carbon laminates, the presence of impact tended to emphasize the importance of interface failures (pull-out and delaminations, Fig. 17) and to localize the damage (Fig. 18). These interface phenomena, together with higher ductility, appeared to be the relevant energy dissipation mechanisms for basalt laminates.

Fig. 17. Typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on basalt laminates impacted at 25J

Hybrid laminates with sandwich configuration (BC-HS) showed, compared with carbon laminates, a higher number of AE signals related to debonding phenomena located mainly in the compression side and due to the basalt skins. These signals were active at low stresses, as reported in Fig. 19.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 18. Acoustic emission localization plot for (a) undamaged and (b) impacted at 25J basalt laminates

Moreover, a higher number of signals characterized by medium to high amplitudes (60-75 dB) and long durations (> 1 ms) related to delaminations was recorded. Basalt skins, characterized by higher deformation, held together the carbon core that, once failed, caused the failure of the whole laminate (Fig. 9b). With increasing impact energy, it is to be noted an increase of signals related to interface failures (Fig. 20). The presence of such delaminations, mainly localized in the compression side, quickly prevented basalt skins from hindering crack propagation in the carbon core, causing its failure. The growing damage localization with increasing impact energy supported what experimentally observed as regards the failure modes of these laminates (Fig. 21). Undamaged hybrid laminates with intercalated configuration (BC-HI) showed a significant number of signals with amplitudes > 60 dB related to delaminations (Fig. 22). With increasing impact energy, a considerable rise in the number of signals at the very beginning of loading along with a growing importance of multiple delaminations occurred.

(a)

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Fig. 19. (a) Typical AE amplitude vs. time response during flexural test on undamaged BC-HS laminates; (b) typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on undamaged BC-HS laminates; (c) amplitude vs. duration response during flexural test on undamaged BC-HS laminates

Fig. 20. (a) Typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on BC-HS laminates impacted at 25J; (b) amplitude vs. duration response during flexural test on BC-HS laminates impacted at 25J

This is highlighted in Fig. 23, which shows the amplitude distribution of AE signals for BC-HI laminates impacted at 25J recorded during the first 110 seconds of flexural loading. Such delaminations are diffused in the material due to higher number of basalt/carbon interfaces. Damage partition among internal interfaces enabled BC-HI laminates, although less resistant than BC-HS hybrids, to show a lower degradation of their strength at higher impact energies, when extensive damage was present. The occurrence of splitting on the rear face, although less evident than in carbon laminates, tended to promote the failure of the outermost fibre layer localized in the tensile side, thus leading to the ultimate failure of the whole laminate.

Fig. 21. Acoustic emission localization plot for BC-HS laminates impacted at 25J. The inset represents a close-up view of typical failure modes for BC-HS laminates impacted at 25J

Fig. 22. Typical AE amplitude vs. time response during flexural test on undamaged BC-HI laminates; (b) typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on undamaged BC-HI laminates; (c) amplitude vs. duration response during flexural test on undamaged BC-HI laminates

This thesis is supported by both the localization of damage that occurred during the last seconds of the test (Fig. 24) compared to the initial loading stages and the transition from a gradual to a more

catastrophic failure mode at the end of flexural test, similar to what observed for carbon laminates.

Fig. 23. Typical amplitude distribution during flexural test on BC-HI laminates impacted at 25J recorded during the first 110 sec

Fig. 24. Acoustic emission localization plot for undamaged BC-HI laminates (a) during the first 110 sec and (b) between 110 and 130 sec

4. Conclusions

The effects of hybridization of basalt fibres on low velocity impact response, damage resistance, and damage tolerance capability of carbon fabric reinforced epoxy composites have been experimentally investigated. Two different hybrid laminate configurations were prepared: one with a sandwich-like stacking sequence and the other with an intercalated fabrics lay-up. The results indicate that the sandwich laminates, though substantially superior in terms of static properties (flexural and interlaminar shear strength), do appear more sensitive to the effect of impact damage. In intercalated hybrids, the higher number of interfaces allows a more effective damage dissipation than on sandwich ones thereby increasing the damage tolerance of carbon laminates.

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